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THE ENTREPRENEURIAL SPIRIT

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In morning light where the sun shines bright,
A man of courage takes its flight,
with vision so bold, he takes his daring quest,
To carve a path, to be the best.

Through winding roads and skies unknown,
The seeds of courage, deeply sown.
With every step, a lesson learned,
Through trial, failure, progress earned.

No fear of risk, no chains of doubt,
The spirit roars, it reaches out.
For strength is found in facing fear,
And courage grows when risk is near.

The world may scoff, the winds may fight,
But still, he rise with endless might.
With trembling hands, yet steady will,
He climb the heights, defying still.

For in his leap, the unknown calls,
A leap of faith, where many fall.
Yet in the daring lies the gain,
The prize that makes the fleeting pain.

An entrepreneur, fierce and free,
The architect of destiny.
With passion's fire and purpose clear,
The path of greatness, always near.

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT EDITORIAL TEAM:

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Managing Editor: Rolando D. Cervantes, DHum

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